

SEX DETERMINATION USING METRIC PARAMETERS OF THE MAXILLARY SINUS: A RETROSPECTIVE STUDY USING CT SCANS OF PATIENTS THAT VISITED RADIOLOGY DEPARTMENT RIVERS STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Retrospective study using CT scans of patients that visited Radiology Department Rivers State university teaching hospital explores the potential of maxillary sinus measurements in sex determination. Examined 140 subjects, comprising 70 males and 70 females, measured the length, height, and width of the maxillary sinuses. Descriptive analysis, sex-wise comparison, and Discriminant function analysis (DFA) were conducted, providing insights into the relationship between sinus dimensions and sex determination. The descriptive analysis revealed that males showed higher mean values for all measured parameters on both sides, the mean right maxillary sinus length, height, and width were 3.780 cm, 3.525 cm, and 2.878 cm, respectively, while the left side measured 3.844 cm, 3.471 cm, and 2.842 cm. In females, the corresponding measurements were lower, with right maxillary sinus values of 3.708 cm (length), 3.321 cm (height), and 2.771 cm (width), and left maxillary sinus values of 3.680 cm (length), 3.297 cm (height), and 2.720 cm (width). The sex-wise comparison showed significant differences in the left maxillary sinus length, right maxillary sinus height, and left maxillary sinus height. DFA revealed that maxillary sinus height, and the left maxillary sinus length showed significant differences among sexes. Maxillary sinus measurements may serve as a useful tool in sexual dimorphism.

KEYWORDS: Maxillary sinus, sexual dimorphism, Discriminant function analysis, CT scan, Retrospective study.

INTRODUCTION

Sex determination remains one of the most fundamental aspects of forensic anthropology and medicolegal identification. Establishing the sex of skeletal remains narrows the search profile by nearly 50%, providing a foundation for subsequent identification procedures such as age estimation, ancestry assessment, and stature reconstruction. Traditionally, the pelvis is considered the most sexually dimorphic bone, followed by the skull; however, in many forensic scenarios, these structures may be unavailable. Natural disasters, explosions,

building collapses, aircraft crashes, intentional mutilation, and wildlife scavenging often leave investigators with only partial remains. This necessitates the exploration of alternative anatomical structures capable of resisting extreme conditions. The maxillary sinus owing to its deep location and bony protection remains one of the most resilient craniofacial structures.^[1,2] Research has consistently shown that skeletal remains can be used to identify gender, as bones are among the last tissues to perish after death.^[3,4]

The maxillary sinus is uniquely suited for this role. It is the largest paranasal sinus and is deeply embedded within the maxilla, providing natural protection from environmental degradation. Its development begins in utero, continues through adolescence, and reaches full maturation by early adulthood. Several studies have demonstrated sexual dimorphism in its morphometric characteristics, making it a potential indicator for gender estimation.^[3,5] shown that the maxillary sinus exhibits sexual dimorphism, with males typically having larger sinus dimensions owing to greater craniofacial pneumatization and hormonal influences during puberty. The anatomy of the maxillary sinus varies in dimensions both between individuals and within the same individual, influenced by factors such as age.^[6] Modern imaging technologies, particularly computed tomography (CT), have revolutionized the field of forensic morphometry. CT provides high-resolution, multiplanar images that allow accurate measurement of sinus dimensions without distortion or magnification errors. It also permits volumetric analysis, reconstruction, and comparison across populations. Unlike plain radiographs, CT can capture complex anatomical contours with minimal superimposition.^[7]

Global studies from India, Egypt, Nepal, the UAE, and Libya have proven that maxillary sinus measurements are reliable indicators of sex. However, sexual dimorphism varies among populations due to genetic, environmental, dietary, and developmental differences. This underscores the need for region-specific forensic standards. In Nigeria, although several anthropometric studies have been conducted, limited research exists on CT-based morphometric analysis of the maxillary sinus for forensic sex estimation, especially within the Niger Delta region.

Therefore, this study aims to fill this gap by evaluating the maxillary sinus dimensions of adults in Rivers State using CT imaging. By analyzing length, width, and height bilaterally and applying discriminant function analysis, this research contributes valuable baseline data for forensic practitioners, anatomists, radiologists, and anthropologists in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A retrospective observational study was conducted using archived CT scans of patients who had undergone paranasal sinus imaging at the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital. A total of 140 subjects (70 males and 70 females) met the criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients referred for computed tomography of the paranasal sinuses but without pathological findings were selected.

Exclusion Criteria

To ensure accuracy in the results, this study excluded subjects with a history of maxillary sinus fractures,

congenital developmental abnormalities, sinusitis, or other sinus pathologies. Additionally, patients without a recorded age or those outside the targeted age range of 20-70 were excluded.

To calculate the sample size using the Taro Yamane^[8] formula:

$$N = N / (1 + N * (e)^2)$$

Given values:

N=sample size

N = population size = 200 using Muthukumaravel et al.,^[9]

E = acceptable sampling error = 0.05

$$1 + N * e^2 = 1 + 200 * (0.05)^2$$

$$= 1 + 200 * 0.0025$$

$$= 1 + 0.5$$

$$= 1.5$$

$$N = 200 / 1.5$$

$$= 133.33$$

Equals; 133 Subjects

The sample size was calculated to be 133, but was increased to 140 (70 males and 70 females) to ensure a more accurate analysis. This allows for a detailed comparison of maxillary sinus measurements between genders and increases the confidence in the results.

Ethical Consideration: Ethical approval was obtained from Rivers State University Teaching Hospital Ethics Committee. Patient confidentiality was maintained as identifiers were excluded.

Additionally, permission was granted by the Head of Department (HOD) of Radiology to access CT scans.

Data Collection and Measurements: The following measurements were obtained in accordance with Desphande et al.,^[10] from scans performed using a GE 64-slice computed tomography machine:

- i. **Width (mediolateral):** The longest distance from the medial wall to the lateral wall of the maxillary sinus was measured in the axial view. (Fig 1)

Fig. 1: Showing measurements of length (A) and width (B) on Axial view.

ii. **Length (anteroposterior):** The longest distance from the anterior wall to the posterior wall of the maxillary sinus was measured in the axial view. (Fig 1).

iii. **Height (superoinferior):** The longest dimension from the superior wall to the inferior wall (floor) of the maxillary sinus was measured in the coronal (fig 2)

Fig. 2: Showing measurements for height (C) on Coronal.

Statistical Analysis

All data were subjected to descriptive analysis, calculating mean, standard deviation, and percentage values. Student's t-test was used to compare data between sexes, with a P value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) considered statistically significant. Discriminant functional analysis and Receiver Operating

Characteristic (ROC) curve analysis were then performed to predict sex based on maxillary sinus dimension measurements. The data analysis was conducted using SPSS software, version 28.

RESULTS

The Results are presented in tables 1-3 and figures.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables (cm).

Variable	Male	Female
	Mean \pm Standard Error	Mean \pm Standard Error
Right maxillary sinus length	3.780 \pm 0.05	3.708 \pm 0.04
Left maxillary sinus length	3.844 \pm 0.04	3.680 \pm 0.04
Right maxillary sinus height	3.525 \pm 0.05	3.321 \pm 0.04
Left maxillary sinus height	3.471 \pm 0.05	3.297 \pm 0.04
Right maxillary sinus width	2.878 \pm 0.06	2.771 \pm 0.04
Left maxillary sinus width	2.842 \pm 0.05	2.720 \pm 0.05

(cm): Centimeter

Table 2: Sex-wise comparison of measurements (cm) (height, length, and width) of maxillary sinus of the right and left side.

Variable(s)	Sex	n	Mean	Std. Error	t-test
Right Maxillary Sinus Length	Male	70	3.780	0.051	t=1.075, df= 138, p=0.284
	Female	70	3.708	0.041	
Left Maxillary Sinus length	Male	70	3.844	0.046	t=2.475, df=138, p=0.015
	Female	70	3.680	0.047	
Right Maxillary Sinus Height	Male	70	3.525	0.053	t=2.870, df=138, p=0.005
	Female	70	3.321	0.046	
Left Maxillary Sinus Height	Male	70	3.471	0.053	t=2.457, df=138, p=0.015
	Female	70	3.297	0.046	
Right Maxillary Sinus Width	Male	70	2.878	0.063	t=1.369, df=138, p=0.173
	Female	70	2.771	0.045	
Left Maxillary Sinus Width	Male	70	2.842	0.058	t=1.483, df=138, p=0.140
	Female	70	2.720	0.058	

Std. Error: standard error, t-test, p-value: significance, n: sample size, df: Degree of freedom

Figure 3: ROC curves to find the optimum cut-off points, sensitivity, and specificity of measures in the identification of sex.

Table 3: Discriminate Function Analysis for length, height and width of maxillary sinus.

Test Result Variable(s)	Area Under the Curve (AUC)	Sig.	Optimum cut-off value (mm)	Sensitivity	Specificity
Right Maxillary Sinus length	0.559	0.228	3.3500	89.0%	82.9%
Left Maxillary Sinus length	0.606	0.031	3.4500	90.0%	74.3%
Right Maxillary Sinus Height	0.635	0.006	3.5600	60.0%	58.0%
Left Maxillary Sinus Height	0.624	0.011	3.3500	68.6%	65.7%
Right Maxillary Sinus width	0.542	0.386	2.5500	75.7%	67.1%
Left Maxillary Sinus width	0.577	0.118	2.3500	82.9%	74.3%

AUC: Area under Curve, mm: Millimeter, Sig: Significant

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of variables: The results indicate that the males had slightly higher mean values of the length, height, and width of the maxillary sinus on both sides.

Table 2: Sex-wise comparison of measurements (height, length, and width) of maxillary sinus of the right and left side: The result showed that there was no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) seen between right maxillary sinus length, right maxillary sinus width, and left maxillary sinus width ($p = 0.284, 0.173, 0.140$) respectively on comparison. However, there was a significant difference seen between the left maxillary sinus length, right maxillary sinus height, and left maxillary sinus height with the corresponding p -values 0.015, 0.005, and 0.015.

Table 3: Discriminate Function Analysis for length, height and width of maxillary sinus: The result of the study showed that the Right Maxillary Sinus Height had the highest value of AUC (0.635), significantly contributed to the prediction model ($p = 0.006$), showed a high sensitivity and specificity of 60.0% and 58.2%, respectively. Left Maxillary Sinus Height had the second highest value of AUC (0.624) also significantly contributed to the prediction model ($p = 0.011$) with

sensitivity and specificity of 68.6% and 65.7% respectively. The Left Maxillary Sinus length with AUC of 0.606, sensitivity and specificity of 90.0% and 74.3% respectively contributed significantly to the prediction model. Whereas, Right Maxillary Sinus length, Right Maxillary Sinus width, and Left Maxillary Sinus width did not significantly contribute to the model.

Length

For males, the present study reports right and left maxillary sinus lengths of 37.80 mm and 38.44 mm, respectively. These values are similar to Indian populations^[10] with values of 38.81 mm and 38.60 mm. However, they are lower than Saudi Arabian males reported by Soman^[5], which are 40.52 mm and 39.40 mm. In comparison, Indonesian males^[1] showed significantly smaller lengths at 28.60 mm and 28.10 mm, suggesting population-specific variations.

Females in the present study displayed lengths of 37.08 mm (right) and 36.80 mm (left), which closely align with Indian populations^[12] reporting 36.93 mm and 37.81 mm.

Libyan females^[13] showed a notably higher left sinus length (40.01 mm), while Indonesian females^[11]

demonstrated the smallest values (25.00 mm and 24.90 mm).

Width

Males in the present study had a mean width value of 28.78 mm and 28.42 mm, closely resembles values from Saudi Arabian males^[5] at 28.35 mm and 28.12 mm. However, it is significantly smaller than Indonesian males^[11] with the highest reported values of 33.50 mm and 37.50 mm.

Comparatively, Libyan males^[13] showed slightly smaller widths at 26.93 mm and 29.02 mm).

Females in the present study (27.71 mm and 27.20 mm) are consistent with Indian populations, such as^[10], reporting 26.03 mm and 25.06 mm.

In contrast, Tamil Nadu females^[14] exhibits smaller widths, with values as low as 21.28 mm and 19.79 mm.

Height

For males, the present study reports heights of 35.25 mm (right) and 34.71 mm (left), consistent with Libyan males^[13] at 36.23 mm and 37.67 mm).

Indian populations^[10] show slightly higher values at 40.57 mm and 40.38 mm, while Indonesian males^[7] reports significantly lower values (27.60 mm and 27.50 mm).

Females in the present study have right and left heights of 33.21 mm and 32.97 mm, closely matching values reported for Nepalese females^[15] at 32.90 mm and 32.30 mm.

Indian females^[16] exhibit much lower values, with the smallest height recorded at 26.20 mm and 26.78 mm.

The variations in maxillary sinus measurements across these populations may be attributed to genetic, environmental, and dietary differences. For instance, higher values in Indian and Saudi Arabian males reflect larger craniofacial structures compared to smaller values in Indonesian and some Egyptian populations. The Nigerian population's measurements align closely with Indian and Nepalese populations, particularly in the female group.

Discriminate Function Analysis (DFA)

The study by^[13] on a Libyan population used various maxillary sinus variables to assess the accuracy of Discriminate Function Analysis (DFA). Their results showed high Area Under Curve (AUC) values, ranging from 0.718 to 0.993, with significant p-values (<0.001) across all variables. The study found varied sensitivity and specificity percentages, with the highest specificity values of 100% for right and left maxillary sinus width (RSW and LSW) but lower sensitivity values, especially for right and left maxillary sinus length (RSH and LSH),

where sensitivity was as low as 52% for RSH. These results show imbalance in sensitivity and specificity.

Desphande *et al.*^[10] conducted a similar analysis on an Indian population from Maharashtra, examining the right and left maxillary sinus length and width. Their AUC values were generally high, ranging from 0.653 to 0.836, with highly significant p-values (<0.001). The study also reported high sensitivity and specificity for all the variables, with sensitivity ranging from 60% to 73.3%, and specificity values of 100% for most variables. This suggests that the DFA model performed well, with a balanced outcome between sensitivity and specificity.

In the present study conducted in Rivers State, Nigeria, the AUC values were lower compared to the studies by^[13] and^[10] with values ranging from 0.542 to 0.635 for various maxillary sinus variables. Although all the p-values were significant (<0.05), they were not as striking as those in the other studies. The sensitivity and specificity values in the present study were higher than those in the^[13] study, particularly for RSL and LSL, with sensitivity reaching 89% for RSL and 90% for LSL. However, the sensitivity values for other variables were still moderate, ranging from 60% to 75.7%. The specificity, though better than some of the other studies, ranged from 65.7% to 82.9%. (Table 3)

The findings from this present study are inconsistent with^[2,12,17] who found no statistically significant differences between Maxillary sinus dimensions, and^[4] who found that the left maxillary sinus was the only significant factor in gender determination.

However, it is important to note that study results may vary due to differences in methods, statistical tools, radiography, sample size, demographics (ethnicity, genetics, environment, race), and anatomical variations in the maxillary sinus.

CONCLUSION

Although maxillary sinus dimensions demonstrate statistically significant sexual dimorphism and moderate discriminatory power in this Nigerian sample, overall accuracy remains lower than in some Asian and North African cohorts. Left maxillary sinus length and bilateral sinus heights are the most useful parameters for sex estimation. Clinicians and forensic experts in sub-Saharan Africa should apply these measures cautiously and preferably in combination with other skeletal indicators until larger, multi-center validation studies are available.

RECOMMENDATION

Future research should involve a larger and more diverse group of people to confirm the reliability of maxillary sinus measurements in identifying sex across different populations. A bigger sample size will improve the accuracy of the results and make them more applicable to various forensic and medical settings.

Including other parts of the skull, such as the frontal sinuses, could also enhance the precision of sex determination methods.

By following these suggestions, future studies can build on the current findings and develop better methods for forensic applications.

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